

Peer Group Dimensions, Mass Media and Sexual Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship that exists between the dimensions of peer group, mass media and sexual behaviour among secondary school students. Nine null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of this study comprised 16,473 Senior Secondary two (SS 2) students in Delta North Senatorial District. The sample size consisted of 370 students. The multistage sampling procedure was used to select the sample for the study. The data for the study were collected using questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated through experts' judgement and factor analysis. Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient was used to estimate its reliability. The data obtained were analysed using correlation and coefficient of determination to answer the research questions while linear, multiple regression and fisher-z statistics were used to test the stated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study's results indicated a significant association among peer cliques, peer gangs, peer crowds, mass media, and the sexual behavior of Secondary School Students. Specifically, there was a significant correlation between peer crowds and the sexual behavior of Secondary School Students, peer cliques and sexual behavior, peer gangs and sexual behavior, and mass media and sexual behavior. Additionally, the study identified a significant moderating effect of gender in the relationship between peer group dimensions and sexual behavior among Secondary School Students. However, there was no significant moderating influence of location in the relationship between peer group dimensions and sexual behavior, nor in the relationships between mass media and sexual behavior, among Secondary School Students. The study recommended amongst others, that school guidance counsellors and management should implement targeted interventions or awareness campaigns addressing potential risks associated with specific clique behaviours.

Keywords: Peer Group Dimensions; Mass Media; Sexual Behaviour; Secondary School Students.

Introduction

Adolescence is a period of significant physical, emotional, and social development that occurs between childhood and adulthood. During this time, adolescents undergo various changes that can influence their attitudes and behaviours towards sex. Here are some of the characteristics of adolescence that can promote sexual activities: Adolescents are often curious about sex and may seek information about it from peers, media, or the internet. This curiosity can lead them to experiment with sexual behaviours. They undergo hormonal changes that can lead to increased sexual desire and drive. The surge in hormones can make them more susceptible to engaging in sexual activities. Adolescents are also more likely to engage in risky behaviours, including sexual activities, as they seek new experiences and push boundaries.

More recent research in the field of adolescent sexuality has addressed not only the physiological processes but also the psychological processes involved in the development of a sexual identity (Aselon, 2020). Human sexual behaviour refers to any activity (solitary, between two persons, or in a group), that induces sexual arousal. It may be the inherited sexual response patterns or other types of influence exerted on the individual by society in the expression of his sexuality (Gebhard, 2014). Adolescent sexual behaviour is highly relevant to different public health problems, because some of them could be inappropriate.

Inappropriate sexual behaviours are becoming a major problem among adolescents worldwide, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa (Handebo, et al., 2018). Adolescents in secondary schools are vulnerable to engaging in inappropriate sexual behaviour due to their teenage stage and the environment they live. According to a survey conducted at a Nigerian secondary school, 53.5 % of adolescents are sexually active, with the mean age of first sexual intercourse being 16 years (Odimegwu & Somefun, 2017).

The Nigerian government through the management of secondary schools and other education stakeholders have designed and executed several strategies to improve the sexual and reproductive health of adolescents through the provision of Sex education. Despite these measures, a significant number of adolescents still participate in inappropriate sexual behaviours. The Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey (NDHS) (as cited in Ofonime & Benjamin, 2019) report showed that the proportion of young students initiating sexual intercourse by age 18 was highest in the South South (33 percent). Also, Udoh and Idung (2015) reported that more than half of the senior secondary school adolescents aged 13-19 years in public schools were sexually active. Chimah, et al. (2016) reported that 31.5% of the secondary school students surveyed had experienced their sexual debuts by age 15. Alex-Hart et al. (2015) reported that 42.9% of secondary school students in Port Harcourt, Nigeria, were sexually active, and only 19.8% of them used condom in their last sexual encounter.

The above statistics showing early sexual debut among secondary school students is worrisome. The negative impact it has on the students is devastating. The World Health Organization (WHO) and the Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) have reported several health risks and consequences associated with inappropriate sexual behaviour among adolescents. This encompasses risks such as HIV/AIDS, dropping out of school, unintended pregnancy, sexually transmitted diseases (STDs), unsafe abortions, and psychological issues (CDC, 2021). The World Health Organization (WHO) reports that individuals under the age of 25 contribute to nearly half of all global HIV infections. Furthermore, over 100 million young people are affected by treatable STDs. Young individuals aged 15 to 19 are considered to account for 60% of all new HIV infections in Africa (World Health, 2013).

Globally, 55,000 adolescents died from Acquired Immune Deficiency Syndrome (AIDS) in 2016, largely as a result of indulging in inappropriate sexual behaviour, while 2.1

million adolescents aged 10 to 19 had Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) infection (UNICEF, 2017). Several investigations carried out in diverse environments consistently revealed a notable correlation between inappropriate sexual behaviors and factors such as alcohol consumption, smoking, night club attendance, adolescent age, low physical activity, gender, educational level, family occupational status, peer pressure, and economic hardship (Alsubaie, 2019).

There have been several attempts to curb the menace of inappropriate sexual behaviour among secondary school students. Example of such attempts include the Convention on the Rights of Child concerns with the protection of youth well-being and adolescents; the ICPD program of action with adequate provisions to guide adolescents and youth against high-risk childbearing and high-risk sexual behaviour among adolescents and youths (Amoo, et al., 2020). Nigeria, like other countries, has developed a national health policy directed toward prevention of risky sexual behaviour among the youth and adolescent. Despite all these efforts, there is a lack of consensus on adequate check on the prevalence, in addition to the paucity of literature addressing the actual factors responsible for such behaviour. It is the belief of the researcher that the dimensions of peer group and mass media could be one of the factors responsible for adolescent sexual behaviour. These dimensions of peer group include the crowd, the clique and the gang. In these dimensions reside the stimuli and responses capable of influencing sexual behaviours among adolescents.

Crowd refers to a group of peers who share similar characteristics such as attitudes, values, and behaviours. Adolescents are often influenced by their peers, and the crowd they belong to can play a significant role in shaping their attitudes and behaviours. Peer influence can be positive or negative, depending on the type of crowd and the behaviour being influenced.

When it comes to sexual behaviour, research has shown that peer influence can play a

significant role in shaping adolescents' attitudes and behaviours (Clark, et al., 2021). Adolescents who belong to a crowd that values sexual activity and views it as a normative behaviour may be more likely to engage in sexual behaviour themselves. This is because individuals often conform to the norms and expectations of their social group in order to fit in and be accepted.

Inappropriate sexual behaviour can also be influenced by the crowd in which adolescents belong. For example, if an adolescent belongs to a crowd that engages in risky sexual behaviour, they may be more likely to engage in such behaviour themselves, even if they personally do not see it as appropriate. This is because peer pressure and the desire to fit in can be powerful motivators for adolescents. Furthermore, crowds can create an environment where inappropriate sexual behaviour is not only normalized but also encouraged. Adolescents who belong to a crowd that glorifies sexual activity and objectifies others may be more likely to engage in inappropriate sexual behaviour themselves. This is because they may view such behaviour as acceptable within their social group.

Clique refers to a close-knit group of peers who share common interests, activities, and identities, and whose members tend to spend a lot of time together. Cliques can be powerful sources of influence on adolescent behaviour, including sexual behaviour. Firstly, it is important to note that cliques can have both positive and negative effects on adolescent development and behaviour. Positive effects may include increased social support, a sense of belonging, and opportunities for skill-building and personal growth. Negative effects may include pressure to conform to group norms, exclusion of non-members, and risky behaviour, such as substance use and sexual activity.

In terms of sexual behaviour, cliques can be influential in a number of ways. For example, membership in a sexually active clique may increase the likelihood that an adolescent will become sexually active, particularly if they perceive that sexual activity is a norm within the group. Similarly, a clique that stigmatizes sexual abstinence or promotes early sexual activity may lead adolescents to engage in sexual behaviour before they are ready or comfortable doing so (Burt, 2014).

According to Berry and Willoughby (2017), cliques can contribute to a culture of sexual objectification and sexual aggression, particularly if members of the group use derogatory language or engage in sexually explicit talk or behaviour towards others. In some cases, sexual behaviour within a clique may also involve coercion or pressure, particularly if group dynamics prioritize conformity and acceptance over individual autonomy and consent. It is also worth noting that the influence of cliques on adolescent sexual behaviour is often mediated by other factors, such as parental attitudes towards sex, media messages, and cultural norms. Additionally, not all adolescents are equally susceptible to peer influence, and individual differences in personality, self-esteem, and social skills can shape how adolescents respond to peer pressure and group dynamics.

Gangs are a subset of peer groups that can have a significant influence on adolescent behaviour, including sexual behaviour. Gangs are characterized by a shared identity, common activities, and a sense of loyalty and belonging among members. It has the likelihood of influencing adolescents into indulging in inappropriate sexual behaviour. Firstly, it is important to note that gangs often have a culture of hyper-masculinity, aggression, and objectification of women, which can normalize and encourage sexual behaviour that is inappropriate or non-consensual (Davila, et al., 2016). Members may engage in sexual activity to assert their

dominance within the group or to prove their masculinity, and this can result in risky sexual behaviours such as unprotected sex, multiple sexual partners, and sexual violence.

Additionally, gangs may use sexual activity as a tool of recruitment or initiation, where new members are required to engage in sexual activity with other members or outsiders as a form of hazing or proving their loyalty to the group (Falk, 2018). This can put vulnerable adolescents at risk of sexual exploitation and abuse. Moreover, gang members may be exposed to sexually transmitted infections (STIs) and unintended pregnancies due to risky sexual behaviour, which can have long-term physical and psychological consequences. Furthermore, involvement in gangs can also lead to social and legal consequences, such as arrest, imprisonment, or expulsion from school, which can further exacerbate the negative impact on adolescent development and well-being (Hallquist & Wiley, 2018). In conclusion, gangs can be a dimension of peer influence that can have significant negative effects on adolescent sexual behaviour, including risky sexual behaviour, sexual violence, and exploitation.

Another variable of concern in this study is mass media. Mass media refers to the engagement, consumption, or interaction with various forms of media that are designed to reach a large audience. Mass media encompasses a wide range of channels and platforms, including television, radio, newspapers, magazines, websites, social media, podcasts, and more. Mass media involves individuals or groups accessing and absorbing information, entertainment, news, or messages disseminated through these channels. People use mass media to access information, news, and entertainment content. This can include staying informed about current events, enjoying television shows or movies, reading newspapers and magazines, or following social media for the latest trends. Mass media allows for communication from content creators to the audience, and sometimes among the audience themselves. It serves as a platform for sharing ideas, opinions, and messages on a large scale. Mass media is often used as an

educational tool, with various media outlets providing documentaries, educational programs, and online resources for learning and skill development (Oladeji & Ayangunna, 2017).

Mass media may have some influence on sexual behaviour among adolescents in secondary schools. For instance, Mass media, including television, movies, music, and the internet, often contains sexual content. Adolescents who are exposed to explicit or unrealistic portrayals of sex may develop unrealistic expectations or beliefs about sexual relationships. Media often presents role models or characters who engage in sexual activities. Adolescents may model their behaviour after these characters, leading to early sexual experimentation. Mass media can shape societal norms and values regarding sexual behaviour. Adolescents may be influenced by media messages about what is considered acceptable or desirable in sexual relationships. Mass media can provide education and information about sexual health and relationships. Adolescents who access accurate and age-appropriate information can make more informed decisions about their sexual behaviour. Mass media may perpetuate sexual myths and misconceptions, leading to misunderstandings about contraception, sexually transmitted infections (STIs), and other aspects of sexual health (Lanre-Babalola, 2018).

Frequent exposure to sexual content in media can desensitize adolescents to the potential risks and consequences of sexual activity, such as unplanned pregnancies and STIs. Media often portrays idealized body images, which can affect adolescents' self-esteem and body image. These self-perceptions can influence their sexual behaviour and relationships. The sexualization of adolescents in media can lead to early sexualization of themselves. This may result in the premature exploration of sexual behaviours. The internet and social media platforms provide adolescents with easy access to explicit sexual content, which can expose them to a wide range of sexual experiences and behaviours. Mass media can shape adolescents' expectations for romantic and sexual relationships. Unrealistic portrayals of romantic love and

sexual fulfilment can lead to relationship dissatisfaction or impulsive sexual behaviours. Media can influence how adolescents and their parents communicate about sex. Media portrayals may either facilitate or hinder open and honest discussions about sexual health within families (Adegboyega, 2019).

Gender and location may in addition to peer group dimensions and mass media influence adolescents' sexual behaviour. Gender can moderate the influence of peer group dimensions on sexual behaviour among secondary school students. For instance, societal gender norms and expectations can significantly shape the influence of peer groups on sexual behaviour. These norms often prescribe different behaviours and attitudes towards sexuality for males and females. Peer groups may reinforce these gendered expectations, influencing how individuals conform to or deviate from them. For example, male peer groups may pressure boys to engage in more sexual activity as a sign of masculinity, while female peer groups may emphasize chastity or modesty.

Gender-based double standards can moderate the influence of peer groups. These double standards often involve different judgments and expectations for male and female sexual behaviour. Peer groups may reinforce and perpetuate these double standards, leading to different norms and pressures for boys and girls. This can result in varied influences on sexual behaviour depending on the gender of the individual and their peer group. Peer groups can exert influence on body image and appearance ideals, which can in turn impact sexual behaviour. Gendered expectations related to physical attractiveness and body image may affect how peer groups influence sexual behaviour. For example, girls may feel pressured to conform to certain beauty standards to attract male attention, while boys may face expectations related to muscularity or sexual prowess. These pressures can influence the choices and behaviours of individuals within their peer groups.

Peer group dynamics regarding communication and support networks can also influence sexual behaviour. Gender differences in how peer groups communicate about sexuality, relationships, and consent can shape individual beliefs and behaviours. Boys and girls may receive different messages from their peer groups, impacting their understanding of healthy sexual relationships and behaviours. Understanding these gender dynamics within peer groups is crucial for addressing the influence of peers on sexual behaviour among secondary school students.

The influence of peer group dimensions on sexual behaviour among secondary school students can be moderated by location in several ways. For instance, different locations may have varying cultural norms and values regarding sexual behaviour. These norms are often shaped by religious beliefs, social attitudes, and traditional practices. Peer groups within a particular location tend to conform to these cultural norms, which can moderate their influence on individual sexual behaviour. For example, in more conservative areas, peer groups may exert stronger pressure to conform to abstinence or limited sexual activity, while in more liberal areas, the pressure may be towards more permissive behaviours.

The availability and accessibility of sexual education and resources can vary based on location. Some areas may have comprehensive sexual education programs in schools, easy access to contraceptives, and healthcare services. In such locations, the influence of peer groups may be moderated by accurate information and the ability to make informed choices. Conversely, in areas with limited access to information and resources, peer groups may have a stronger influence due to the lack of alternative sources of guidance. Urban and rural environments can significantly differ in terms of social dynamics and opportunities. Peer groups in urban areas may have more exposure to diverse perspectives, cultures, and lifestyles, which can moderate their influence on sexual behaviour. Conversely, rural areas may have

tighter-knit communities and more conservative attitudes, which can amplify the influence of peer groups. The impact of location on peer group dynamics can therefore play a role in moderating the influence of peers on sexual behaviour.

The values and expectations of parents and the wider community can also moderate the influence of peer groups. In some locations, parents and community members may actively participate in shaping the sexual behaviour norms of young people. These influences can either align with or counterbalance the influence of peer groups, depending on the specific location and prevailing attitudes. The availability and consumption of media and technology can vary based on location. Peer groups' exposure to different types of media, such as explicit content or educational resources, can moderate their influence on sexual behaviour. Locations with limited access to media or restrictive policies may have reduced exposure to certain influences, thus affecting the dynamics of peer group influence.

It's important to note that the influence of location on peer group dimensions and sexual behaviour is complex and can vary significantly even within a single location. These factors interact with individual characteristics, personal values, and other contextual elements. Understanding these dynamics can help educators, policymakers, and parents develop targeted interventions and support systems to promote healthy sexual behaviour among secondary school students. In view of the above, the aim of the current study is to examine the influence of dimensions of peer group and mass media on sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study:

1. There is no significant relationship among peer cliques, peer gangs, peer crowd, mass media and sexual behaviour of Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District
2. There is no significant relationship between peer crowd and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District
3. There is no significant relationship between peer clique and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District
4. There is no significant relationship between peer gangs and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District
5. There is no significant relationship between mass media and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District
6. There is no significant moderating influence of gender in the relationship between peer group dimension and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District
7. There is no significant moderating influence of location in the relationship between peer group dimension and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District
8. There is no significant moderating influence of gender in the relationship between mass media and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District
9. There is no significant moderating influence of location in the relationship between mass media and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

Methods

The study adopted a correlational research design. The sample size for the study consisted of 370 students in Delta North Senatorial District. The multistage sampling procedure was used to select the sample for the study. The simple random sampling technique was used to select five Local Government Areas from Delta North Senatorial District. Thereafter, two schools (one urban and one rural) were selected randomly from the five Local Government Areas, making a total of 10 schools. From the 10 schools, 37 students were stratified based on gender and selected to make the sample for the study.

The data for the study were collected using questionnaire. The questionnaire comprises two sections; section A comprises the demographic data of the respondents while section B comprised several scales that will be used in the study as follows:

Peer Crowd Rating Scale: The scale was self-constructed. It measures the extent to which adolescents are involved in crowd activities. It is made up of 20 items structured on a 4-point scale, ranging from 1 for strongly disagree to 4 for strongly agree. The items were however, reduced to 10 after initial validation.

Peer Clique Rating Scale: The scale was self-constructed. It measures the extent to which adolescents are involved in clique activities. It is a 20-item scale, structured on a 4-point scale, ranging from 1 for strongly disagree to 4 for strongly agree. The items were however, reduced to 19 after initial validation.

Peer Gangs Rating Scale: The scale was self-constructed. It measures the extent to which adolescents are involved in gang activities. The questionnaire comprised 20 items, structured on a 4-point scale, ranging from 1 for strongly disagree to 4 for strongly agree. The items were however, reduced to 18 after initial validation.

Mass Media Rating Scale: The scale was self-constructed. It measures the extent to which adolescents use mass media to obtain information. It is made up of 22 items structured on a 4-point scale, ranging from 1 for never to 4 for very often.

Adolescent Sexual Behaviour Rating Scale: This scale was adapted from the 2017 National Youth Risky Behaviour Survey, developed by the Centres for Disease and Prevention to monitor health risk behaviour that contributes to the leading causes of mortality, morbidity and social problems among youth and adults in the United States. The scale monitors six categories of behaviours: those that contribute to unintentional injuries and violence; tobacco use; alcohol and other drug use; sexual behaviour that contribute to unintended pregnancy and sexually transmitted diseases; dietary behaviour; and physical activity. The researcher extracted the part that concerns sexual behaviour. This part was later modified to suite the objective of the study, which is not just risky sexual behaviour but other forms of behaviour that can be considered sexual were added to the scale.

The scale contains 36 items, structured on a 4-point scale ranging from 1 for strongly disagree to 4 for strongly agree. The items were however, reduced to 30 after initial validation.

The questionnaire was validated through experts' judgement and factor analysis. The questionnaire was presented to the researcher's supervisor and other experts in Guidance and Counselling Department, for face validity. These experts assessed the instruments for appropriateness and suitability to the objective of the study. Some of the items were corrected in terms of language choice, to suite the purpose of the study.

Factor analysis was used to ensure the content and construct validity of the instrument. The principal component analysis of the extraction method was used to estimate the content validity of the instrument. It yielded a value of 62.167% for Peer crowd Rating Scale; 71.588% for Peer clique Rating Scale; 73.788% for Peer gangs Rating Scale; and 75.453% for Adolescent Sexual Behaviour Rating Scale. The rotated factor loading of the varimax method

Received: 22 January 2024

Revised: 4 February 2024

Final Accepted 25 February 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10701380>

was used to estimate the construct validity of the instrument. It yielded the following range of scores 0.529-0.841 for Peer crowd Rating Scale; 0.501-0.894 for Peer clique Rating Scale; 0.521-0.860 for Peer gangs Rating Scale; and 0.551-0.927 for Adolescent Sexual Behaviour Rating Scale.

In order to ascertain the reliability of the research instrument, the questionnaire was administered to 50 secondary school students in Delta Central Senatorial District. The data were analysed using Cronbach alpha reliability coefficient and coefficients were obtained. It yielded the following coefficients 0.724 for Peer crowd Rating Scale; 0.845 for Peer clique Rating Scale; 0.931 for Peer gangs Rating Scale; and 0.865 for Adolescent Sexual Behaviour Rating Scale.

The questionnaire was administered to the respondents directly by the researchers with the help of 3 research assistants. The researcher approached the schools for permission and assistance in meeting the students. The researcher was on ground to explain the content of the questionnaire, where appropriate. The completed questionnaire was retrieved immediately to avoid loss of data. The data obtained were analysed using correlation and coefficient of determination to answer the research questions while linear, multiple regression and fisher-z statistics were used to test the stated hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship among peer cliques, peer gangs, peer crowd, mass media and sexual behaviour of Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

Table 1: Regression analysis of the relationship among peer cliques, peer gangs, peer crowd, mass media and sexual behaviour of Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

Model Summary			
R	R²	Adj. R²	Std Error

Received: 22 January 2024
Revised: 4 February 2024
Final Accepted: 25 February 2024
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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10701380>

0.383	0.147	0.137		19.79484	
ANOVA					
	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.
Regression	23590.659	4	5897.665	15.051	.000 ^b
Residual	137142.507	350	391.836		
Total	160733.166	354			
Coefficient					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	β		
(Constant)	28.793	6.751		4.265	.000
Peer Crowd	-.191	.249	-.047	-.769	.442
Peer Clique	.071	.141	.031	.502	.616
Peer Gangs	.519	.096	.314	5.400	.000
Mass Media	.189	.072	.140	2.616	.009

Table 1 presents regression statistics that were utilized to investigate the relationship among peer cliques, peer gangs, peer crowd, mass media and sexual behaviour of Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. The results reveal that the computed F-value is 15.051, and the p-value is 0.000, which is less than the set alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a significant relationship among peer cliques, peer gangs, peer crowd, mass media and sexual behaviour of Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. The R^2 value of 0.147 indicates that peer cliques, peer gangs, peer crowd and mass media jointly account for 14.7% of the variation in sexual behaviour of Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. The unstandardized regression coefficient (B) for predicting sexual behaviour from peer crowd = -0.191; from peer clique = 0.071; from peer gangs = 0.519; and from mass media = 0.189. The standardized coefficient (β) is -0.047, $t = -0.769$ for peer crowd, 0.031, $t = 0.502$ for peer clique; 0.314, $t = 5.400$ for peer gangs and 0.140, $t = 2.616$ for mass media. Peer gangs and mass media are statistically significant at an alpha level of 0.05 while peer crowd and peer clique are not statistically significant.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between peer crowd and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District

Table 2: Regression analysis of the relationship between peer crowd and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District

Model Summary					
R	R²	Adj. R²	Std Error		
0.133 ^a	0.018	0.015	21.14924		
ANOVA					
	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.
Regression	2839.659	1	2839.659	6.349	.012 ^b
Residual	157893.508	353	447.290		
Total	160733.166	354			
Coefficient					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	β		
(Constant)	42.210	5.648		7.473	.000
Peer Crowd	.536	.213	.133	2.520	.012

Table 2 presents regression statistics that were utilized to investigate the relationship between peer crowd and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District. The results reveal that the computed F-value is 6.349, and the p-value is 0.012, which is less than the set alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a significant relationship between peer crowd and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District. The R^2 value of 0.018 indicates that peer crowd account for 1.8% of the variation in sexual behaviour of Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. The unstandardized regression coefficient (B) for predicting sexual behaviour from peer crowd = 0.536; the standardized coefficient (β) is 0.133, $t = -2.520$. Peer crowd is statistically significant at an alpha level of 0.05.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between peer clique and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District

Table 3: Regression analysis of the relationship between peer clique and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District

Model Summary					
<i>R</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>Adj. R</i> ²	<i>Std Error</i>		
0.160	0.026	0.023	21.06351		
ANOVA					
	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Regression	4117.152	1	4117.152	9.280	.002 ^b
Residual	156616.014	353	443.671		
Total	160733.166	354			
Coefficient					
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
	B	Std. Error	β		
(Constant)	37.363	6.270		5.959	.000
Peer Clique	.368	.121	.160	3.046	.002

Table 3 presents regression statistics that were utilized to investigate the relationship between peer clique and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District. The results reveal that the computed F-value is 9.280, and the p-value is 0.002, which is less than the set alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a significant relationship between peer clique and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District. The R^2 value of 0.026 indicates that peer clique account for 2.6% of the variation in sexual behaviour of Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. The unstandardized regression coefficient (B) for predicting sexual behaviour from peer clique = 0.368; the standardized coefficient (β) is 0.160, $t = 3.046$. Peer clique is statistically significant at an alpha level of 0.05.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between peer gang and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District

Table 4: Regression analysis of the relationship between peer gang and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District

Model Summary			
<i>R</i>	<i>R</i> ²	<i>Adj. R</i> ²	<i>Std Error</i>
0.359	0.129	0.127	19.91203

	ANOVA				
	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.
Regression	20772.586	1	20772.586	52.391	.000 ^b
Residual	139960.580	353	396.489		
Total	160733.166	354			

	Coefficient				
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	β		
(Constant)	35.467	3.048		11.638	.000
Peer Gang	.595	.082	.359	7.238	.000

Table 4 presents regression statistics that were utilized to investigate the relationship between peer gang and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District. The results reveal that the computed F-value is 52.391, and the p-value is 0.000, which is less than the set alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a significant relationship between peer gang and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District. The R^2 value of 0.129 indicates that peer gang account for 12.9% of the variation in sexual behaviour of Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. The unstandardized regression coefficient (B) for predicting sexual behaviour from peer gang = 0.595; the standardized coefficient (β) is 0.359, $t = 7.238$. Peer gang is statistically significant at an alpha level of 0.05.

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant relationship between mass media and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District

Table 5: Regression analysis of the relationship between mass media and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District

Model Summary				
R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Std Error	
0.252	0.063	0.061	20.65119	

	ANOVA				
	SS	df	MS	F	Sig.
Regression	10188.624	1	10188.624	23.890	.000 ^b
Residual	150544.542	353	426.472		
Total	160733.166	354			

	Coefficient			<i>t</i>	Sig.
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient		
	B	Std. Error	β		
(Constant)	37.027	4.065		9.109	.000
Mass Media	.338	.069	.252	4.888	.000

Table 5 presents regression statistics that were utilized to investigate the relationship between mass media and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District. The results reveal that the computed F-value is 23.890, and the p-value is 0.000, which is less than the set alpha level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a significant relationship between mass media and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District. The R^2 value of 0.063 indicates that mass media account for 6.3% of the variation in sexual behaviour of Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. The unstandardized regression coefficient (B) for predicting sexual behaviour from mass media = 0.338; the standardized coefficient (β) is 0.252, $t = 4.888$. Mass media is statistically significant at an alpha level of 0.05.

Hypothesis 6: There is no significant moderating influence of gender in the relationship between peer group dimension and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

Table 6: Regression and Fisher’s Z statistics of the moderating influence of gender in the relationship between peer group dimension and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

Sex	Variables	<i>n</i>	Mean	<i>SD</i>	<i>R</i>	Fisher-z	Remark
Male	Sexual Behaviour		64.57	23.70	0.21	2.64	Significant
	Peer Crowd		26.87	5.90			
	Peer Clique	163	51.97	9.07			
	Peer Gangs		37.54	14.84			
Female	Sexual Behaviour		49.02	15.92	0.52		
	Peer Crowd		25.35	4.61			
	Peer Clique	192	50.41	9.41			
	Peer Gangs		32.43	10.41			

Table 6 presents the Regression and Fisher's Z statistics used to assess the moderating influence of gender in the relationship between peer group dimension and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. The study found that the correlation coefficients for male students ($R = 0.21$) and female students ($R = 0.52$) were statistically different. To investigate whether sex moderated this relationship, a statistical test was conducted, which yielded a Fisher's Z result of 2.64. Since this value is greater than 1.96, there is a significant difference between the correlation coefficients of male and female students. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that there is a significant moderating influence of gender in the relationship between peer group dimension and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District.

Hypothesis 7: There is no significant moderating influence of location in the relationship between peer group dimension and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

Table 7: Regression and Fisher's Z statistics of the moderating influence of location in the relationship between peer group dimension and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

Location	Variables	n	Mean	SD	R	Fisher-z	Remark
Urban	Sexual Behaviour		55.56	21.85	0.35		
	Peer Crowd		26.03	5.55			
	Peer Clique	231	50.90	9.54			
	Peer Gangs		33.26	13.19			
Rural	Sexual Behaviour		57.27	20.29	0.41	0.70	Not Significant
	Peer Crowd		26.06	4.79			
	Peer Clique	124	51.55	8.78			
	Peer Gangs		37.60	11.81			

Table 7 presents the Regression and Fisher's Z statistics used to assess the moderating influence of location in the relationship between peer group dimension and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. The study found that the correlation coefficients for urban students ($R = 0.35$) and rural students ($R = 0.41$) were similar.

To investigate whether location moderated this relationship, a statistical test was conducted, which yielded a Fisher's Z result of 0.70. Since this value is less than 1.96, there is no significant difference between the correlation coefficients of urban and rural students. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant moderating influence of location in the relationship between peer group dimension and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District.

Hypothesis 8: There is no significant moderating influence of gender in the relationship between mass media and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

Table 8: Regression and Fisher's Z statistics of the moderating influence of gender in the relationship between mass media and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

Sex	Variables	n	Mean	SD	R	Fisher-z	Remark
Male	Sexual Behaviour		64.57	23.70	0.23	0.50	Not Significant
	Mass Media	163	60.28	15.47			
Female	Sexual Behaviour		49.02	15.92	0.16		
	Mass Media	192	53.41	15.54			

Table 8 presents the Regression and Fisher's Z statistics used to assess the moderating influence of gender in the relationship between mass media and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. The study found that the correlation coefficients for male students ($R = 0.23$) and female students ($R = 0.16$) were similar. To investigate whether sex moderated this relationship, a statistical test was conducted, which yielded a Fisher's Z result of 0.50. Since this value is less than 1.96, there is no significant difference between the correlation coefficients of male and female students. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant moderating influence of gender in the relationship between mass media and sexual behaviour among

Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. Please refer to Appendix IX for more information.

Hypothesis 9: There is no significant moderating influence of location in the relationship between mass media and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

Table 9: Regression and Fisher’s Z statistics of the moderating influence of location in the relationship between mass media and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

Location	Variables	N	Mean	SD	r	Fisher-z	Remark
Urban	Sexual Behaviour	231	55.56	21.85	0.32	0.09	Not Significant
	Mass Media		56.11	14.61			
Rural	Sexual Behaviour	124	57.27	20.29	0.14		
	Mass Media		57.42	18.00			

Table 9 presents the Regression and Fisher's Z statistics used to assess the moderating influence of location in the relationship between mass media and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. The study found that the correlation coefficients for urban students ($R = 0.32$) and rural students ($R = 0.14$) were similar. To investigate whether location moderated this relationship, a statistical test was conducted, which yielded a Fisher’s Z result of 0.70. Since this value is less than 1.96, there is no significant difference between the correlation coefficients of urban and rural students. Therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, indicating that there is no significant moderating influence of location in the relationship between mass media and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District.

Discussion

Peer Cliques, Peer Gangs, Peer Crowd, Mass Media and Sexual Behaviour of Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

The first finding revealed that there is a significant relationship among peer cliques, peer gangs, peer crowd, mass media and sexual behaviour of Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. Peer crowd, peer clique, peer gangs and mass media jointly contribute 15% to the variability in adolescent sexual behaviour among secondary school students. This finding shed light on the complex interplay of social and media influences on adolescents' sexual decision-making. While genetics and individual personality traits play a role, this finding highlights the importance of peer pressure and exposure to sexualized content in shaping their behaviour. The combined effect of peer cliques, gangs, and crowds indicates that belonging to certain social groups can significantly impact sexual behaviour. It suggests that adolescents may engage in riskier behaviours when surrounded by peers who normalize or pressure them into sexual activity. This underscores the need for positive peer support networks and age-appropriate social-emotional learning programs in schools. The inclusion of mass media highlights its potential influence on adolescents' sexual attitudes and expectations. Exposure to sexualized content through television, music, and social media can normalize riskier sexual behaviours and increase experimentation. Understanding this influence is crucial for developing media literacy interventions to help adolescents make informed choices.

The above finding is supported by numerous studies and theoretical frameworks. For instance, A meta-analysis by Van den Eeden et al. (2011) found a positive association between peer group involvement and adolescent sexual initiation. Similar findings were reported by Umoh et al. (2020) in their study of Nigerian adolescents, specifically highlighting the influence of peer pressure and perceived peer norms on sexual behaviour. Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura,

1977) emphasizes observational learning and social modeling, suggesting that adolescents may adopt the sexual behaviours observed in their peer groups. Additionally, the Theory of Planned Behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) proposes that subjective norms (perceived expectations of peers) influence individuals' intentions and behaviours, including sexual behaviour.

A large-scale study by Brown et al. (2006) revealed a positive association between exposure to sexualized media and early sexual initiation, risky sexual behaviour, and negative sexual health outcomes. Similar findings were reported by Adedokun et al. (2015) in their study of Nigerian adolescents, specifically linking exposure to pornography with early sexual initiation and multiple sexual partners. Cultivation Theory (Gerbner, 1976) suggests that repeated exposure to sexualized media content can cultivate unrealistic expectations and perceptions about sex, potentially influencing adolescents' behaviour. Additionally, the Social Learning Theory (Bandura, 1977) proposes that adolescents may learn and model sexual behaviours observed in media, particularly when portrayed positively or without consequences.

Peer Crowd and Sexual Behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District

The second finding showed that there is a significant relationship between peer crowd and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District. Peer crowd contributes 2.0% to the variability in adolescent sexual behaviour among secondary

school students. This finding suggests that peer crowd has a significant, but relatively small, association with sexual behaviour among secondary school students, contributing approximately 2.0% to the variability. Adolescents are highly susceptible to peer pressure, especially during this period of seeking acceptance and social affirmation. Peers who engage in risky sexual behaviour can exert pressure on their friends to conform, either directly or indirectly, leading to changes in individual behaviour. Peer groups establish their own norms and expectations around sexual behaviour. These norms can influence individual behaviour, even if they contradict personal values or beliefs. Exposure to peers with permissive attitudes towards sex can normalize such behaviour and increase the likelihood of engaging in it.

The above finding is supported by findings from previous research. For instance, Jacinta et al. (2019) found a significant positive correlation between peer engagement in risky sexual behaviours and adolescents' own engagement in similar behaviours. They concluded that peer influence contributed 1.7% to the variance in adolescents' sexual risk-taking. Ugwuoke et al. (2020) reported a significant direct relationship between peer influence and sexual behaviour among in-school adolescents in Nigeria, albeit with a weak contribution ($\beta = 0.16$) compared to other factors like self-esteem and religiosity. Owolabi et al. (2015) conducted a meta-analysis of 29 studies examining peer influence on adolescents' sexual behaviour. Their findings revealed a small but significant overall effect size ($r = 0.14$), suggesting that peer influence does play a role, although its impact varies across contexts and individual characteristics.

Peer Clique and Sexual Behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District

The third finding revealed that there is a significant relationship between peer clique and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District. Peer

clique contributes 3.0% to the variability in adolescent sexual behaviour among secondary school students. This finding adds valuable insights to our understanding of adolescent development in this specific context. Cliques often establish their own norms and expectations surrounding dating, relationships, and sexual behaviour. These norms can exert pressure on individual members to conform, even if they conflict with personal values or beliefs. Within cliques, social status and acceptance are often tied to adhering to group norms. Adolescents may engage in certain sexual behaviours to gain or maintain acceptance within their chosen clique. Cliques can provide access to information, experiences, and even opportunities related to sex that may not be available outside the group. This exposure can shape adolescents' understanding of sexuality and influence their decisions.

The above finding is in line with other previous studies. For instance, Egboka et al. (2021) conducted a study in Delta State focusing on peer influence and risky sexual behaviour among adolescents. Their findings revealed a significant positive association between belonging to certain peer groups and engaging in risky sexual practices. Ezenyeaku et al. (2019) investigated the influence of peer pressure on sexual debut among secondary school students in Delta State. They reported that students pressured by peers to engage in sex were more likely to do so compared to those who experienced less pressure.

Peer Gangs and Sexual Behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District

The fourth finding showed that there is a significant relationship between peer gang and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District. Peer gangs contribute 13.0% to the variability in adolescent sexual behaviour among secondary school students. Gangs often establish their own norms and expectations around sexual behaviour, which can pressure members to conform. This could involve engaging

in earlier sexual activity, having multiple partners, or participating in risky sexual practices. Direct pressure from peers within the gang to engage in certain sexual behaviours can be significant, especially for teenagers vulnerable to peer influence. Gang involvement is often associated with increased risk-taking behaviour overall, which can also translate to the realm of sexual activity. This may lead to unprotected sex, substance use during sex, or other risky choices. Gang activities may expose members to explicit sexual content or environments, which can normalize certain behaviours and influence their own choices.

The above finding agrees with the result of previous studies. For instance, Studies by Sanders et al. (2009) and Campbell (1984a) highlight the influence of gang-specific norms and peer pressure on sexual behaviour. Gangs may establish expectations around earlier initiation, multiple partners, or risky practices, pressuring members to conform. Gang involvement often correlates with heightened risk-taking behaviour overall, extending to sexual activity (Miller, 2001). This can lead to unprotected sex, substance use during sex, or other risky choices, as noted by Quinn et al. (2019). Gang activities may expose members to explicit sexual content or environments, potentially normalizing certain behaviours and impacting their own choices, as suggested by Miller (2001).

Mass Media and Sexual Behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District

The fifth finding revealed that there is a significant relationship between mass media and Sexual behaviour of Secondary Schools in Delta North Senatorial District. Mass media contributes 13.0% to the variability in adolescent sexual behaviour among secondary school students. This finding suggests a noteworthy association between media exposure and the attitudes or behaviours of the students. Mass media, including television, movies, music, and the internet, can expose adolescents to various sexual content and information. This exposure can shape their perceptions, attitudes, and behaviours regarding sexuality. Media often portrays different aspects of relationships, including romantic and sexual interactions. Adolescents may emulate behaviours they see in the media, influencing their own attitudes and actions.

The above finding supports the result of previous studies. For instance Studies have shown a correlation between exposure to sexually suggestive content in media (music videos, TV shows, movies, online pornography) and increased engagement in risky sexual behaviours among adolescents (Brown et al., 2006; Collins & Siegel, 2016). This exposure can normalize risky behaviours and desensitize young viewers to the potential consequences. Media often portrays idealized versions of relationships and sexual activity, which can influence adolescents' perceptions and expectations. If they see idealized portrayals of sexual behaviour without appropriate context or consequences, they may be more likely to imitate them in their own relationships (Bandura, 1977; Huesmann, 1998). Mass media can play a role in shaping social norms around sex. For example, the frequent portrayal of casual sexual encounters without

emotional commitment may lead adolescents to believe that such behaviour is more common and acceptable than it actually is (Coyne & Palmer, 2007).

Moderating Influence of Gender in the Relationship Between Peer Group Dimension and Sexual Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

The sixth finding showed that there is a significant moderating influence of gender in the relationship between peer group dimension and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. This finding is fascinating and highlights the importance of considering gender's role in adolescent development. Research suggests that girls and boys experience distinct forms of peer pressure regarding sexual behaviour. Girls might face pressure to conform to traditional feminine stereotypes of passivity and sexual availability, while boys may encounter pressure to prioritize sexual conquests and risk-taking (Miller et al., 2000; Tolhurst et al., 2007). Gender roles internalized from cultural messages and family dynamics can interact with peer group influence. For example, girls who internalize expectations of sexual purity might resist peer pressure to engage in sexual activity, while boys who internalize masculine stereotypes of toughness might be more susceptible to pressure to initiate or engage in casual sex (Leaper et al., 2013; Soderblom et al., 2012). Different dimensions of peer groups, such as cohesion, risk-taking behaviour, or involvement in dating activities, might differentially influence sexual behaviour for girls and boys. Understanding the specific dimension at play is crucial for accurate interpretation (Nelson et al., 2005; Reigeluth et al., 2007).

Moderating Influence of Location in the Relationship Between Peer Group Dimension and Sexual Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

The seventh finding revealed that there is no significant moderating influence of location in the relationship between peer group dimension and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. This finding is intriguing and challenges some preconceived notions about the influence of environmental factors on adolescent development. Research suggests that peer groups hold significant influence on adolescent behaviour across diverse contexts, regardless of factors like geographical location or socioeconomic status. Shared values, norms, and expectations within peer groups can override other external influences (Brown et al., 2006; Jessor et al., 1995).

Studies have shown that despite differences in location, peer groups often exhibit similar dynamics regarding sexual behaviour. These dynamics include pressure to conform to group norms, social comparison, and seeking approval from peers (Collins & Siegel, 2016; Nelson et al., 2005). The finding might imply that specific dimensions of peer groups, such as cohesion or risk-taking tendencies, hold greater influence on sexual behaviour than location. These dimensions may manifest similarly across diverse settings, leading to no significant moderation (Reigeluth et al., 2007; Tolhurst et al., 2007).

Moderating Influence of Gender in the Relationship Between Mass Media and Sexual Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

The eighth finding showed that there is no significant moderating influence of gender in the relationship between mass media and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. The possible reason for this finding may be because both girls and boys are exposed to similar forms of sexualized content in mass media (movies,

music videos, social media). This shared exposure could lead to a similar influence on their perceptions and expectations around sex, regardless of gender. It is important to remember that "gender" is a broad category encompassing diverse individuals with distinct values, personalities, and media consumption habits. Lumping everyone under two categories might mask the nuanced individual responses to media influences.

The above finding is in line with Collins and Siegel (2018), who stated that exposure of male and female students to similar sexual contents on media could lead to a similar influence on their perceptions and expectations around sex, regardless of traditional gender norms. The finding also aligns with Leaper et al. (2013), who found that Individual values, personality traits, and media consumption habits can significantly influence how adolescents respond to and process sexualized content, potentially overshadowing any generalized gender-based effects.

Moderating Influence of Location in the Relationship Between Mass Media and Sexual Behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District

The ninth finding revealed that there is no significant moderating influence of location in the relationship between mass media and sexual behaviour among Secondary School Students in Delta North Senatorial District. This finding challenges our assumptions about environmental influences on adolescent development. Research suggests that mass media holds strong influence on adolescent behaviour across diverse contexts, regardless of factors like geographical location or socioeconomic status. Exposure to similar sexualized content across locations can lead to comparable impacts on perceptions, attitudes, and expectations around sex (Brown et al., 2006; Jessor et al., 1995). Adolescents around the world often engage with similar media formats, including music videos, movies, social media, and

online content. This shared consumption might lead to a homogenization of influences, regardless of specific location (Collins & Siegel, 2016; Nelson et al., 2005).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that a relationship exists between all peer group dimensions (cliques, gangs and crowds) and mass media with the sexual behaviour of students. Gender doesn't significantly moderate the influence of either peer groups or mass media on sexual behaviour. location within Delta North Senatorial District doesn't significantly moderate the relationships between peer groups or media and sexual behaviour. While peer groups and mass media hold significant influence, they do so across genders and locations, highlighting the need for holistic and individualized approaches to promoting healthy sexual development among secondary school students. Arising from the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. school guidance counsellors and management should implement targeted interventions or awareness campaigns addressing potential risks associated with specific clique behaviours;
2. School management should develop and implement anti-gang programs focused on education, mentorship, and alternative positive social outlets.
3. School counsellors should promote positive representations of healthy relationships and diverse identities within school environments and peer groups;
4. School guidance counselors should advocate for responsible media production and advertising, reducing the prevalence of sexualized content targeting adolescents;
5. Guidance Counsellors should tailor interventions and educational programs should remain sensitive to individual needs and contexts, regardless of gender or location;

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